

“Understanding Political Participation of Women in Urban Local Governance: Evidences from Guwahati Municipal Corporation, Assam”

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Abstract:

Women's standing in society is mostly determined by their involvement in politics, representation in elected offices, and share in decision-making bodies. Women's political engagement as representatives in decision-making bodies is extremely low in the majority of the world's nations. Particularly in the wealthy and developing nations, the situation is appalling. While some well-chosen women with a solid political experience may hold senior executive and political positions or participate in decision-making bodies, this does not necessarily mean that women are becoming empowered. In this paper an attempt has been to study the political participation women with special reference to Guwahati Municipal Corporation (GMC) Assam.

Keywords: Status of Women; Representation; Underdeveloped; Pathetic; Empowerment.

Introduction:

Scholars have extensively examined the concept of political involvement from a variety of viewpoints, including socioeconomic, political, and scholarly. The word "political participation" is linked to the word "political," which means to examine the use of power. Political participation, in this context, refers to the exercise of power through involvement in the political system at different levels. Political participation is defined as the range of actions carried out by someone holding an elected office or doing their civic duty. This is due to the expectation that such involvement will serve as a platform for public decision-making, which is characterised as power. Political engagement has historically been restricted to involvement in official political institutions, such as legislatures and the executive branch in democracies. Political theorists have expanded it to encompass movements, protests, and struggles as acceptable manifestations of political behaviour. Political engagement, then, is any action that a person takes to directly express their political beliefs.

Urban Local Governance:

The management of local affairs by duly elected bodies that serve the local people is known as local self-government. In India, there are two types of local self-governance: urban local government and rural local government. The urban local government manages affairs in towns and cities through municipal corporations, committees, councils, cantonment boards, town and notified area committees, and other municipal entities. The 74th Constitutional Amendment Act (CAA)'s Article 243 Q (1) defines the three different types of urban local bodies: nagar Panchayats for transitional areas, municipal councils or boards for smaller urban areas, and municipal corporations for bigger areas. According to the 74th Constitutional Amendment Act, all states have allocated one-third of their population to women and Schedule Caste and

Schedule Tribe reservations, with members of municipal councils being chosen directly for a five-year term. Based mostly on population, the overall number of members in municipal bodies varies from state to state. In Maharashtra, for instance, the overall strength of municipal corporations is 65-227, whereas in Guwahati, Assam, the entire strength is 60.

Objectives:

1. To highlight the participation of women as elected members in the GMC.
2. To make a brief study of the post 74th Constitutional Amendment scenario in the context of participation of women.

Study Area:

In Guwahati, GMC, Assam is the only urban local body in charge of overseeing 216 square kilometres of GMC territory. The Assam Legislative Act of 1969 allowed for the establishment of the GMC, which began operations in 1974. There are 60 wards in the GMC overall.

Methods and data collection:

This paper is mainly based on secondary sources of data. Data has been collected from the GMC office and from other relevant literatures like books, journals, etc. The method of this study is mainly analytical.

Women's Participation in Electoral Politics:

The Indian Constitution guarantees the right to vote for all adults and establishes the conditions necessary for women to actively engage in politics. Religion, race, caste, sex, and place of birth are among the grounds on which discrimination is forbidden by Article 15 of the Constitution. Despite this constitutional provision, women's involvement in state and national politics as candidates, voters, legislators, and holders of portfolios in various political organizations is still insufficient. Only 18 women from Assam have been elected to the Lok Sabha from 1952 -2024. Besides, in Assam Legislative Assembly, only 93 women has been

elected from 1952-2021. In the recently held Assam Legislative Assembly election, 2021, only 74 women candidates out of 946, who contested for 126 seats. Only 7.8% candidates were women. This is very minimal figure in a democratic country like India where all people irrespective of sex are considered as equal. And only 12 women candidates have contested the 2024 Lok Sabha elections in Assam. The scenario of less participation of women as representatives is similar to that of other states of India. However the percentage of women as voters is encouraging.

Dhaneswar Baishya says “the participation of women in the electoral process has been very

insignificant. There are no legal obstacles in the participation of women in the electoral process but in reality there still exists some socio- economic obstacles”. The need of the hour is to make the women conscious of their rights and also of their role in politics and the importance of women’s participation in the decision making process.

In the GMC, we found that the participation of women in the electoral process as voters is quite remarkable but as an elected representative is not satisfactory, basically before the introduction of 74th Constitutional Amendment Act (CAA), 1992.

Table 1.1 Number of Elected Women Representatives of GMC before the Introduction of Reservation Policy through 74th CAA

Year of Elections	Number of wards for election	Number of contesting women candidates	Number of Elected Women Representatives	Introduction of Reservation Policy through 74 th CAA
1974	34	0	0	No
1979	34	4	0	No

Source: GMC Election Report

The table clearly indicates that no women have been elected in the GMC elections before the introduction of reservation policy of women. However, a total of 4 women candidates have contested in the 1979 election of GMC, but not a single woman was able to win a seat. This is because due to the believe that

“Politics is meant only for men, household chores are meant only for women”. Still the society runs in this notion where men are capable to play active role in decision making and women are good house makers.

Table 1.2 Number of Elected Women Representatives of GMC after the Introduction of Reservation Policy through 74th CAA

Year of Elections	Number of wards for election	Number of Women candidates	Number of Elected Women Representatives	Introduction of Reservation Policy through 74 th CAA
1995	60	36	19	Yes
2003	57	57	19	Yes
2013	31	72	10	Yes
2022	60	110	30	Yes

Source: GMC Election Report

The table clearly shows that after the introduction of 74th CAA, the number of women contesting candidates’ increases. The introduction of 74th CAA has created a space for women in the GMC, urban local governance. In the first three elections of GMC, as per the 74th CAA, 33 % of seats were reserved for women in urban local governance but the Assam Government has introduced 50 % of reservation of seats for women in the 2022 election. Consequently, the number of women of both contesting and winning seats was raised to 110 and 30 respectively. The 74th CAA has truly provided a platform for women to participate actively in the grassroots level of politics which is considered as the learning arena for regional and national level of politics.

Conclusion:

Based on the aforementioned study, it can be concluded that the 74th CAA has created opportunities for women to actively engage in urban municipal governance. Correcting an unfair and unrepresentative system is just as important as promoting parity when it comes to women in positions of leadership. The secret to equitable economic growth is political transformation. Since the new members have a bigger stake in the local natural resources, local councils are likely to be more environmentally protective as a result of the local self-government transforming them into representative entities.

In India, urban local governance gives women a chance to transform the political leadership landscape. However, we still need to

make sure that these are areas where women can go to bargain for their rights.

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